

Relevance of Indus Valley Civilization's Pacifism in the emergence of Thoreau and Gandhian morality

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Abstract: The accepted modern doctrine of political philosophy declares that a fully peaceful society is not possible. This presumption has, understandably, been made by many influential thinkers of the past and present. The prevailing consensus is that pacifism does not work as a sustainable political system. However, this modern consensus does not explain the flourishing of the Indus Valley civilization (IVC). IVC which lasted for 500 years, in its mature state, from 2600 BCE to 1900 BCE, was a predominantly peaceful and egalitarian society as per the archeological evidence known today. It remains a mystery how the Indus people maintained peaceful living for a period of 500 years. What model of political theory can account for the pacifism and or egalitarianism of the Indus Valley? Understanding the political and philosophical system of the Indus Valley will be of tremendous help to bring solutions to our modern complex political system which is pushing us towards conflict, climate change, and inequality. The reasoning behind this peaceful existence could be explained by a variety of explanations but is likely the result of a shared core philosophical belief system. We have used a focus group discussion (FGD) and Satavata-tarka (Suppositional reasoning) methods to brainstorm weekly for 15 sessions. The themes that emerged during FGD were organized through grounded theory, and then Satavata-Tarka (1-2) was applied for the emergence of a core theme. We evaluated two contrasting ideas of history development: linear progression vs cultural emergence, where periodic chaos is followed by the emergence of pacifism through a process of Cultural Emergence (1-2). The discussion resulted in the emergence of a few themes, including the possible continuity of IVC's core knowledge system in modern India. Even after 1900 BCE, the core ideas of CVSSs influenced the later civilizations such as those during the Vedic period (1500 BCE - 500 BCE) which in turn influenced both classic (600 BC - 400 AD) and post-classic (after 400 AD) India, and even those farther abroad, such as the transcendentalism found in the 19th century American thought (Thoreau), and the political-philosophy of non-violence, "satyagraha" (Gandhi). Thus, the possible widespread influence of the Indus Valley's pacifistic society in the contemporary world suggests an alternative model of political philosophy, where the knowledge emergence process may initiate and sustain peace.

Introduction

The accepted modern doctrine of political science declares that a fully peaceful society is not possible. This presumption has, understandably, been made by many influential thinkers of the past who lacked the breadth and depth of historical information available today. Thomas Hobbes, for example, upon witnessing the English Civil War, came to believe that society needs a strong central authority to tame humanity's naturally rebellious spirit. Thucydides, Thomas Hobbes, Machiavelli, and contemporary political philosopher Stephen Walt, all share the idea that the desire for wealth and power is human nature, and therefore conflict between nations is inevitable. This is one of the main reasons for the establishment of the Westphalian principles of sovereign state, and non-interference in the political system of neighboring states to maintain international peace. On the other hand, the Realistic school or the post-Westphalian or Liberalism school believes that human barbarism needs to be controlled by powerful and ethically strong states, which should interfere with nation-states that act immorally including gross violation of human rights. Indeed, Tony Blair advocated in 1999 the doctrine of the international community to take forward the era of globalization smoothly by interfering in the state sovereignty of states resistant to globalization.

Modern liberals take inspiration from John Locke, who, in 1689, declared that individuals are born in a blank state without any preordained ideas: the barbaric state of Nature (John Locke, *Two Treatises of Government*; <https://socialsciences.mcmaster.ca/.../locke/government.pdf>). Immanuel Kant provided a strong argument for this notion in his seminal work, *To Perpetual Peace*. Simply, Kant theorized that democratic governments would stay away from war or conflict with other nations to ensure re-election. Joseph Nye @Harvard and Bob Keohane took forward this idea to propose the theory of interdependence and cooperation that ties democratic nation-states together as one international system. Thus, both the Realism and Liberalism spectrum of modern political theories are rooted in one single assumption: human nature is inherently barbaric, and sinful; therefore, the rightful government should be chosen by democratic citizens to elect a body of enlightened beings to govern them. Indeed, the overwhelming international consensus is that the democratically elected civil government's moral job is to change the barbaric nature of humans to a civilized one by ensuring basic human rights of freedom, health, and wealth, and these should be imposed by war or peaceful election in states that refuse to comply with this notion.

Thus, in the evolutionary history of the Westphalian system, we find the concept of "rightful king" as the moral insight, where only some chosen one is enlightened, the rest are as per John Locke, barbaric. This is a very powerful political philosophy, as it can explain the world's history in a nutshell: human beings are naturally barbaric, and need a holy system, either an organized religion or a state to keep them civilized. For example, the Mesopotamian King Sargon of Akkad (2300 BC) who is now considered as Middle East's first dictator, destroyed the Sumerian city-states as per his notion of Sharru-kin (rightful King). Sargon rose to power by defeating another dictator, Lugalzagesi, the ruler of Sumer, who also declared the rightful king chosen by the goddess Enlil, "When Enlil, the king of all the lands, gave the kingship of the Land to Lugalzagesi, he justified "eyes" of the Land...." Nippur vase inscription of Lugalzagesi, 2330 BC.

What new is possible at the fundamental core of international relations? What new is possible against the backdrop of what Kant and Locke sealed through their seminal work: the “barbarian natural state”?

This question brings us to the paradox of the Indus Valley civilization, an ancient civilization of India that shows no sign of king or war in its 2000 years of archaeological evidence scattered among nearly 25 major city-states, where 5 million people lived in its height, (~2500BC). One of the most prominent, and also most mysterious, of these examples, is the Indus Sarasvati civilization. This civilization existed in its mature stage from 2600 to 1900 BC. The civilization comprised a vast network of cities and villages twice the size of the contemporary Egyptian and Mesopotamian civilizations. More than 25 large (more than 200 acres) and organized cities with a population of more than 50,000 have been identified, each having paved roads, drainage systems, public baths, and meeting halls, as well as individual homes equipped with toilets. Additionally, more than 1000 medium to small-sized cities have been so far identified. None of the cities contain large-scale monuments for kings or nobles, a characteristic of the contemporary bronze-age civilizations of Egypt and Sumer. Graveyards are mostly filled with ordinary items, such as pottery, without any distinct characteristic between commoners and high-ranking people, indicating an egalitarian tendency of the society. Evidence of a large-scale army, or weapon cache has not been identified, although each home contained usual household weapons such as knives required for domestic work. Although large walls and citadels are identified, the role of these structures in defense formation is most unlikely. Moreover, there was uniformity of artifacts and symbols throughout the civilization, and the 500 years of growth indicated the existence of law, ethics, and a standard form of governance that regulated public activities. In its entire corpus of artwork, there is no depiction of warfare, and archeologists still have yet to find any weapons used for warfare, despite knowing that they were very skilled in metallurgy and other craftworks. These evidences indicate that Indus people lived in a political system of pacifism and or egalitarianism. (3-8).

The Indus Valley presents a major challenge to the modern doctrines of historiography and sociology in regards to its lack of a “leviathan” and peaceful existence.

Interestingly, many of the aspects of the Indus Valley continue to flourish in cultural India, including the non-violence or Ahimsa philosophy that Gandhi utilized for India’s independence movement against British Colonialism. Interestingly, Gandhi was influenced by Thoreau’s ideal of civil disobedience, a philosophy inspired by Thoreau’s interaction with Hindu philosophy as mentioned in his masterpiece of writing, the Walden Pond. Interestingly, Gandhi and Thoreau’s teaching influenced India’s remote village Sualkuchi’s evolution of the Jiva Upakara Vada, a tantra-based philosophy on pacifism (<https://lincolnsquirrel.com/2023/08/my-turn-connecting-rural-india-to-walden-pond-through-healthcare-research-and-cultural-development/>). Gandhi visited the village Sualkuchi in 1946, and was inspired by the age-old weaving culture, including the Muga silk weaving, which was probably initiated in Indus Valley civilization. Traces of muga silk have been found in Indus valley archaeological sites. The Muga

Silk museum of the Sualkuchi village has been actively engaged in focused group discussion on Indus Valley culture as a part of the general interest in pacifism, and social altruism as described in this news story (<https://lincolnsquirrel.com/2023/08/my-turn-connecting-rural-india-to-walden-pond-through-healthcare-research-and-cultural-development/>) and a research paper on the link between contemporary Hindu knowledge system and IVC knowledge system (2).

Therefore, we hypothesized that a focused group discussion-based study in the cultural setting of Walden Pond, as well as the Muga Silk Museum, Sualkuchi will enable the emergence of new themes of research to study the cultural and political dimensions of Indus Valley civilization.

Methodology: We have used a focus group discussion (FGD) method to brainstorm the likelihood of political and philosophical theories that prevailed in the Indus cities. Within the FGD sessions, we practiced Satavata-tarka, an Indian knowledge system-derived technique of suppositional reasoning. FGD sessions were held around Walden Pond, including in the Red Rail Farm; a total of 15 sessions were held, where SK, BD, SD, CS, MB, and KM actively participated. 4-5 sessions were also held in India's Suad Muni campus of KaviKrishna Laboratory. The emerging themes were coded, and then through grounded theory, major patterns of discussions were analyzed, evaluated, and re-analyzed for a comprehensive interpretation of our discussions.

Results: A year of discussion resulted in the emergence of a few themes. These themes have been organized through grounded theoretical methods. Through this series of FGD sessions, we found that the philosophical system had pacifism at its core. Even after 1900 BCE, this philosophical system influenced the later civilizations such as those during the Vedic period (1500 BCE - 500 BCE) which in turn influenced both classic (600 BC - 400 AD) and post-classic (after 400 AD) India, and even those farther abroad, such as the transcendentalism found in the 19th century American thought (Thoreau), and the political-philosophy of non-violence, "satyagraha" (Gandhi).

Indus valley and pacifism

The Indus Valley civilization grew to become one of the world's greatest ancient civilizations, though it began as a collection of small camps and farming villages. Geographically, it spanned parts of present-day India, Pakistan, and Afghanistan, while temporally, it spanned centuries (3-4). The Indus Sarasvati was contemporary to the early stages of the Mesopotamian civilization, and the Egyptian old kingdoms. Its size greatly outnumbered any of its competitors; in 2200 BC, the major Indus cities had a combined population of 5 million – five times the size of Egypt and Mesopotamia combined. Egypt and Mesopotamia, as well as other contemporary civilizations, were all violent; In general, the larger and more organized the society, the more larger and more organized the acts of violence.

The cities along the Indus Sarasvati river were well-planned and advanced, as they developed the world's first systems of running water and plumbing system. Additionally, the

‘Harrapans,’ or people of the Indus valley, developed a common script: the Indus valley script (which remains untranslated to this day). According to modern-day computational analysis, the majority of the Indus’ written materials follow a similar pattern, suggesting languages and art also had similar styles throughout the basin. The evidence would suggest ample communication and connection between different regions of the civilization. Usually, with connection comes conflict, power games, and ultimately, war. However, there has not been a single depiction of warfare found in the entire corpus of uncovered artwork. In addition, archaeologists have not found any evidence of weapons used for warfare despite knowing that the people were highly skilled in metallurgy and other craftworks—based on the advanced metal tools such as the 33 surgical tools found—. The pacifism was certainly not due to isolation, as Indus cities were well-connected as we can see from Indus influence in Mesopotamia and central Asia. It wasn't a lack of military technology either; the craftsmen were highly skilled. There’s even been a document displaying 33 different surgical tools found. Bribery would not have been sustainable. For some reason, each individual chose not to act on violence of their own accord. Thus, it is likely a philosophical reason that stands at the root of this perplexing case. Indeed, in more recent pacifist societies, such as the Cathars or Jains, a universal, accepted philosophy seems to be of vital importance to the maintenance of peace.

Around 1900 BCE, the Indus Valley urban centers started to decline and the writing system has since been lost. Mentioning of the Indus Valley in Mesopotamian inscriptions suggests it (what is) is likely known as Meluhua or possibly Marakasi. The oldest Hindu texts, such as the Vedas, also contain stories that predate this "collapse;" the Vedas mention the Sarasvati river, which dried up around 3900 years ago. Whether this indicates that the Harappans were Aryans or simply coexisted with the Aryans, and thereby how the collapse of the civilization came about, is up for debate. Climate change and the general Bronze Age collapse of contemporary civilizations are also being considered. Regardless of the model used for its collapse, one can examine the society’s pacifistic foundations. Likely in part due to its mysterious collapse, there seems to be less known about this ancient civilization in comparison to its counterparts. There are a number of archeological sites, but unfortunately, only around 5% have been excavated. Further research might help to decipher the extensive scripts that are currently left untranslated and is imperative in understanding the implications of society in the modern day. Interestingly, Muga silk fiber has been found in IVC sites (7-8) raising the possibility of a trade route between IVC cities and Kamarupa, the North Eastern frontier province of ancient India (2).

By combining archeological and literary evidence as well as comparative and descendant analysis, one can theorize how the Indus Valley maintained its society. Based on current archeological and historical evidence, the Indus Valley civilization was most likely pacifistic and had an archaic state, or a nonstate complex society (3-5). There are three points of evidence that suggest a philosophical motivation; comparative analysis shows that almost all successful peaceful societies have a predominant transcendental philosophy, two the presence of transcendental art such as the Shiva seal or the dancing girl seals, as well as swastika and Manadala symbols (5,8)—this suggests a predominance of transcendental gods—, and third the records of transcendental religion in the epic Mahabharata, these three reasons form the core of the argument for why a

philosophical reason for pacifism is likely as opposed to an external motivation such as bribery or coercion. The transcendental pacifism concepts existed in the East that were not found in the West: the concept of a supreme heavenly force or Rta or Dharma, and the concept of an eternal soul. These two concepts are linked in their hierarchical nature, as the soul dominates the body just as the deity dominates the earth. The presence of “transcendental religion,” religion where spirit is predominant both in cosmology and in the self, is supported by archeological evidence from the Indus Valley showing meditation figures and characters interpreted as proto shiva, a heavenly deity. Although transcendentalist concepts do not always bring about pacifism, they can be a key component in pacifistic decentralized societies: e.g., religious communes, Cathars, Jains, etc. The transcendentalist elements of Hinduism, Jainism, and Buddhism, (or dharmic thought more generally), formed the core of the Indus Valley religion and are likely a key component in their pacifism. From the art, such as the seals, we can see the presence of Indo-European mythology and quite possibly a continuous worship of Shiva, exemplifying continuity between Indus Valley thought and later Indian religion/philosophy. Thus, it would make sense that the pacifistic ideologies were transferred in this continuous stream of thought as well. Regardless of what was specifically the case in the Indus Valley, it is likely that this pacifism has influenced modern philosophies of India.

Classical and post-classical India

Going on in time from the Indus Valley we see a slow transformation from the urban centers of the Harrapans to the agricultural societies of what is called the Vedic period in India (9-10). The Vedic period lasted roughly from 2000 BC to 600 BC during this time there were many changes such as the Vedas being written down for the first time: hence the name. But despite these changes, the core axioms of thought regarding the self the world, and what to do persisted. We can track this from the perspective of transcendental pacifism.

Madhu Vidya is one of the best examples of Vedic pacifism his thought can be encapsulated in the statement “I am the honey of the world and the world is the honey for me”; Mahidas advocated that violence disrupted this harmonious relationship his ideas can be seen in the Aitareya Upanishad (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aitareya_Upanishad). Two other Upanishads can be used to support this claim Brihadaranyaka https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brihadaranyaka_Upanishad and Chandogya https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chandogya_Upanishad) Upanishads. The sadhus of India followed in the way of Madhu vidya this thought sprouted Vratya traditions (11) which in turn sprouted both orthodox sects of pacifism like yoga and heterodox sects of pacifism like Jaina. Probably the best example of pacifism is the Samanic sect Jainism, where believers and practitioners do not eat anything that would kill anything (including plants) the monks wear masks to not inhale bugs and sweep the road in front of them. This is an extreme version of pacifism, but regardless trend can be seen in other sects such as yoga and Buddhism. In fact this pacifistic religion sprouted the first major uptick in vegetarianism from Japan to Greece from 200 BC to 800 AD vegetarians sprouted up around the world.

Moving later in time to the classic age from 600 BC to 600 AD we see three main paradigms promoted first the Samkhya tradition which promoted dualism and asceticism based on said dualism (9-10). It is debated whether or not Kapila (the founder of Samkhya) was a vegetarian—vegetarianism being a good marker of pacifism— but many of his successors were from. Other movements of the time such as Vaisheshika stressed the importance of karma and dharma as tenets both promoting pacifism. By 400 BC the Sramanic movements gained popularity and Buddhism, Jainism and other Sramanic philosophical movements were on the rise. These political philosophies, as well as spiritual movements, promoted both pacifism and vegetarianism. In fact we can see from foreign accounts such as that of Greek historians that “they prided themselves on “never having been invaded and never invading any foreign countries”. Later on, two Chinese Buddhist monks, Faxian and Xuanzang traveled extensively in India and India and wrote about the kingdoms of India even having abolished any form of capital punishment and how the people in the societies were free to go and leave as they pleased (10). This directly mirrors the Indus Valley pacifism.

Later Adi Shankara, the legendary philosopher converted India back to orthodox Vedic thought but still pacifism was the dominant philosophy (9-10) so much so that when later on in the post-classical period the Muslims came, the Indians were starkly unprepared and defeated in wars after wars with minimal resistance. It is important to note that we are not claiming there were no wars let alone no violence simply that the dominant philosophy of the time was one of transcendental pacifism.

Contemporary pacifist movements of Thoreau and Gandhi:

During the FGD, one recurring theme was Thoreau and Gandhi’s ideas of transcendentalism and Satyagraha. In the 19th and 20th centuries of political philosophic influencers, both Thoreau and Gandhi were the two giant outliers. Although the follower of liberalism admires both, as Philip Abbott rightly pointed out (<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2131071>), Thoreau is anything but liberal, as unlike liberals, Thoreau insisted on a self, which is noble and virtuous, the Brahman of Veda and Gita (<https://yogainternational.com/.../why-did-thoreau-take.../>). Across the globe in Concord Massachusetts, in 1845, Henry David Thoreau, developed a unique philosophy influenced by Indian philosophical texts he read while studying at Harvard. Thoreau was born in 1817, the third child of a poor family. He was a gifted student, though disliked its ranking system, preferring the school library for his intellectual passions. He realized at an early age his boredom in the plain village he resided in, though his love for the woodlands, streams, and wildlife around him never ceased. Disdainful of the life he feared he was conforming to, having spent a few years, after Harvard, working in his father’s business making pencils, Thoreau decided to separate himself from society entirely and return to mankind’s roots in the woods. In the two years Thoreau spent on Walden Pond, he discovered for himself and for many scholars to ponder for centuries, the true problem with his materialist society.

Thoreau's isolate experiment was greatly influenced by his friend Ralph Waldo Emerson whom Thoreau met for the first time giving a lecture to a crowded house at Harvard in 1830. Emerson touched Thoreau greatly, and they became close friends. Emerson ignited Thoreau's love and appreciation for Indian religious and philosophical texts. During the summer of 1840, Thoreau found *The Laws of Manu* on Emerson's bookshelf, and wrote that they come to him with such a volume of sound as if it had swept unobstructed to me over the plains of Hindustan, and when my eye rests on yonder birches, or the sun in the water, or the shadows of the trees, it seems to signify the laws of them all. They are the laws of you and me, a fragrance wafted down from those old times and no more to be refuted than the wind." Thoreau considered the *Laws of Manu* and the *Bhagavad Gita* to be "divine" and they contain "stupendous and cosmogonic philosophy." Thoreau's ideas of the "lives of quiet desperation" being lived in his unspiritual village of Concord, was reinforced through the concept of "Samsara," the belief of cyclical and mundane lives of wandering with no existence caused by lack of good karma. Thoreau observed that most people in his society lived empty lives caused by unfulfilling work, lack of leisure time, and misplaced values: money, possessions, and accolades. They surrendered to their circumstances and felt no duty or purpose in their lives. The *Upanishads*, another crucial text reinforcing Thoreau's beliefs, speaks of this, through the idea that the universal soul (brahman) resides in the individual (atman), creating the ultimate purpose for humans to have. Thoreau is described as always having a connection to his land, and the blissful nature of Concord though, and his veneration for it was reinforced by the ideas of *Madhu Vidya*, that by connecting to one part of nature, you connect to everything. It was in this idea that Thoreau appreciated to even greater degrees on his experiment at Walden, that founded his core beliefs in how we should live our lives: in intimate connection with the natural world, and self-reliance and purpose. Along with this, came Thoreau's adoration for routine bathing, as he compared his own Walden Pond to be "at least as sacred as the Ganges" (A sacred river in Northern India) Hinduism believes that bathing in the river of Ganges on certain occasions is vital for the forgiveness of sins and to attain salvation. Not only is one cleaning their own physical body but attempting to do of their lives and soul as well. Thoreau's daily bath in Walden Pond wasn't something done for appearance, but rather a daily renewing of "thyself completely each day." It was an opportunity to start new and forget the negativity of one's past.

Thoreau's most significant discoveries living on Walden Pond and through his life as a whole can be separated into two different categories: those of the self and purpose, and those of civilization and government. With this, however, his criticisms of particular aspects of his society fit in both of these categories. Through Thoreau's understanding of Indian Philosophy and Hinduism and its evolution from the culture of Indus Valley Civilization, a connection, although questionable, can be made between Thoreau's ideas pertaining to civilization, and the structure of the Indus Valley Civilization. What's more important to acknowledge though is how the Indus Valley's structure which through Indian philosophy influenced Thoreau, was expanded, and developed by his own experiences. In the Indus Valley Civilization, there was a lack of rigid

classes or a hierarchy, and the people worked with purpose and duty. Thoreau despised the hierarchy he saw in his society where “The virtues of a superior man are like the wind; the virtues of a common man are like the grass; the grass, when the wind passes over it, bends.” In the Indus Valley, the community worked for a collective goal, and men were given work because they had skills in that trade and wanted to. Through these ideas of a greater meaning than survival and work influenced the divine Indian texts that Thoreau read, inspiring his unique perspective on the individual’s role in society. Thoreau found that the men in his society worked under a mistake. “The better part of the man is soon plowed into the soil for compost. By a seeming fate, commonly called necessity, they are employed, as it says in an old book, laying up treasures which moth and rust will corrupt, and thieves break through and steal. It is a fool's life, as they will find when they get to the end of it, if not before.” Thoreau strongly believed in both the past paragraphs and just now, that men have “no time to be anything but a machine,” but this continued over to his strong views against slavery. Thoreau believed that men have a duty to themselves and “others to follow what is deemed right, rather than what is created by fallible laws.” Indus Valley Civilization was also egalitarian and therefore, probably against slavery, but now Thoreau pioneered a new idea, civil disobedience. Thoreau strongly opposed the idea that the government should “meddle in the issues of the morality,” adding, “I’m a man first and a subject.” To Thoreau, the individual is the center of moral progress, and the government shouldn’t interfere with one’s free will or conscience. In 1846, Thoreau was jailed for refusing to pay a poll tax on the grounds that the money might be used to pay for the Mexican American war. He opposed this war as it was purely for financial gain and to expand slavery. He accepted his jailing saying, “Under a government which imprisons any unjustly, the true place for a just man is also a prison.” The last major similarity between the two societal structures was the lack of archeological evidence on corporal punishment present in the Indus Valley Civilization and in Thoreau’s ideal society. In the Indus Valley Civilization, the people lived freely and in peace because of their obedience to a common goal, eliminating the need for corporal punishment. Similarly, Thoreau quit his job as a schoolteacher after two weeks because he refused to use physical discipline on students, again, working and supporting only the institutions and governments that reflected his beliefs.

Gandhi

Moving forward in time, we see the influence and convergence of many streams of thoughts on pacifism all stemming from the Indus Valley. Gandhi represents and symbolizes the continuity of this thought process and the “cultural emergence” of India’s unique pacifism. From the thought of the classical Vedic age, and classical India of the Gupta period to the thought of Bhakti gurus, Thoreau, and the transcendentalists, a pacifist society of Indus Valley civilization can be imagined that supports recent finds of Indology regarding the Indus Valley. All this continuous living tradition of pacifism converged and synergized in the figure of Mahatma Gandhi. Gandhi's philosophy—satyagraha— or soul power incorporated concepts of yoga, Jnan (knowledge), and transcendentalist movements of Thoreau and Emerson. In fact, Gandhi himself imagined a society parallel to the Indus Valley.

Followers of liberalism greatly admire Gandhi (<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2131071>), although, unlike John Locke's view on barbaric human nature, Gandhi viewed human nature as noble and wise. Gandhi, an ideal Hindu philosopher came to this conclusion naturally from his Hindu cultural background, where the Natural state of an individual is "sat chit Ananda" or bliss, but not John Locke's barbarism. So, where did Thoreau and Gandhi find so much confidence to project their thought? Is it the Cultural Emergence of the Indus Valley Civilization? In the FGD session, BD talked about his writing on Gandhi: "In 1903, when Gandhi came from South Africa to India to fight against the British Empire, he found Hindu culture disintegrated into its thousands of parts; there was nothing to unify the diversified cultures of Hindus. Gandhi traveled throughout India for years, read its history, communicate with people, and then finally came up with a very unique idea to unify the Hindu culture. He launched the Swaraj movement and used the Charkha (spinning wheel) as a symbol of unity, asking all men and women of India to spin at least for half an hour a day: the message was that Ram Raj can be achieved by spinning wheel and living a noble life. Robindranath Tagore, a Nobel Prize-winning poet from Bengal (an eastern province of India), reacted angrily, "Has it (the spinning wheel) really the divinity which may enable it to appropriate the single-minded devotion of all the millions of India, despite their diversity of temperament and talent? Tagore's argument made sense; how can a spinning wheel unite the people of India? However, Gandhi persisted with his plan, liberated India, and reestablished the Indian nation, which is now, an emerging power of the world and, a stable democratic force. Gandhi was a visionary leader who sensed that the spinning wheel symbolized a new, subtle, and yet continuous Cultural Emergence process, which has been operating in India since the time of the Indus Valley Civilization" (1). One notable aspect of the Gandhian view is the rural instead of urban civilizational strength. Gandhi viewed rural India as the core strength of a civilizational morality. Gandhi viewed that moral power cannot emerge from cities because of greed and corruption that forces city dwellers to live relatively immoral lives. Considering that IVC was mostly urban, it seems that as per Gandhi's view, non-violent and moral ideologies such as pacifism may not emerge from IVC's urban living. However, recent evidence indicate that IVC was largely a rural civilization (PMID: [33223574](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33223574/)).

Hypothesis generation:

One way to explain the emergence of Thoreau and Gandhi is the theory of Cultural Emergence as described previously (1-2). As per this theory, the Indus Valley civilization was knowledge-based and continued to the modern age through the process of Knowledge Emergence. Briefly, Emergence is a property of the self-organized system. In the self-organized system, very simple interactions within the local community may evolve as a higher order; this process of self-evolving is known as Emergence (the flocking of birds is an example of Self-organization, and Emergence is an inherent property of self-organization). Knowledge, once emerging in the Indus

cities and villages, did not die; it passed from generation to generation through oral traditions, rituals, and temporal-self continuity of Indus culture. To comprehend this view on IVC, we need to conceptualize the knowledge emergence process. Knowledge emergence is a continuous flow of information from the past, through the present to the future, and it involves a community rather than an individual, as knowledge Emerges through social interaction in a given community through the process of self-organization. Human cognition cannot be considered in isolation from the community, rather it is part of the past and present of the culture of the given community. The social communication, the life of a society (its past, present, and future), and the individual cognition are all interconnected. The interaction, when reaching a threshold may be self-organized and eventually Emerge as a knowledge system to regenerate and revive the collective memory of the community, which eventually leads to Cultural Emergence.

The revival of India through Gandhi's independence movement is an example of Cultural Emergence through the process of knowledge emergence, which revived the spirit of non-violence embedded in the Indus-Valley civilization. To understand Gandhi's movement we need to read our previous article on Knowledge Emergence (1), "Historically, during the 7th-8th century AD, Hindu culture was flourishing on the subcontinent as well as in South East Asia. From the 8th to 12th centuries, however, the culture disintegrated and Islamic invaders destroyed the network of its indigenous systems, including universities and temple complexes. For a couple of centuries, there were no signs of regeneration, and the Hindu culture seemed to follow the path of decay and death of its contemporaries Egyptian and Sumerian cultures that long died. However, something different happened to Hindu culture. From the beginning of 14th century, a pattern of regeneration emerged and spread throughout India, illustrated in the intense efforts to translate the Ramayana epic into regional languages and make it available as a means of belief and teaching for the common people. Regional cultures began to flourish and villagers emerged as translators, poets, and singers of the Ramayana in almost every corner of India. One common element of all the translations was the intense effort to reconnect with the ancient knowledge and moral power of India. The translation of the Ramayana followed the translation of other scriptures and epic stories. Curiously, these different translation activities occurred spontaneously amongst diverse communities spread throughout the subcontinent without any communication with each other, or any national leader or central command. The translation process was a self-evolving, self-organized act of revival of the Hindu knowledge system. The revival of the knowledge system led to the generation of *Cultural Emergence*, and within a period of time, new spiritual movements, such as Sikhism, Vaishnavism (in Bengal and Assam), and warrior sects like Maratha, emerged with new strength and vitality." British invasion and colonization during 19th century again led to disruption of the *Cultural Emergence* process. In 1903, when Gandhi came from South Africa to India to fight against the British Empire, he found Hindu culture disintegrated into its thousands of parts; there was nothing to unify the diversified cultures of Hindus. Gandhi traveled throughout India for years, read its history, communicated with people, and then finally came up with a very unique idea to unify the Hindu culture. He launched the *Swaraj* movement and used the Charkha (spinning wheel) as a symbol of unity, asking all men and women of India to spin at least for half

an hour a day: the message was that Ram Raj can be achieved by spinning wheel and living a noble life. Robindranath Tagore, a Nobel Prize winning poet from Bengal (an eastern province of India), reacted angrily, “Has it (the spinning wheel) really the divinity which may enable it to appropriate the single-minded devotion of all the millions of India, despite their diversity of temperament and talent?” [26] Tagore’s argument made sense; how can a spinning wheel unite people of India? However, Gandhi persisted with his plan, as he sensed the pervading aesthetic, spiritual, and military force of Hindu *Cultural Emergence* ongoing in the sub-continent since the medieval period and enhanced the process through intensified social interaction through mass praying, the spinning wheel, and discussions about epics such as Bhagavat Gita, Ramayana and Mahabharata. Gandhi instilled the dream of “Ram Rajya” of Ramayana epic among the masses, thus amplifying the social interaction and networking process. Gandhi’s efforts led to a healthy, non-violent process of self-organization as the millions of people felt connected to spiritual India or the knowledge beam (Figure 3, reference 1 or Figure 5 reference 2). A hidden India emerged as a powerful nation. Gandhi’s independent movement was a self-organized process to revitalize the indigenous knowledge system, which integrated the *Cultural Emergence* process and generated enough power to unite a disintegrated culture. Gandhi was a visionary leader who sensed that the spinning wheel symbolized a new, subtle, and yet continuous *Cultural Emergence* process, which has been operating in India since the Indus Valley civilization. Thus, Gandhi’s non-violent movement for India’s independence is a good example of the revival/regeneration of the spirit of the Indus Valley civilization. The knowledge system of Shrudas could be traced back to Indus Valley civilization” (2).

Further research

Examining the pacifism of each of the classic philosophies and other strands of communication to the modern-day, and then connecting these threads to develop a modern socio-political theory is the next aim of our FDG sessions for the year 2024-25. In this context, we need to re-examine Bourdieu's Social Topography (12) as well as social reconstruction theory of Indra-Jaal (Indra Net) of Jiva Upakara Tantra (13). We intend to continue with the FDG to include the domain of philosophy to science strategy of Thoreau Lab for Global Health as submitted to the Government of India (14).

Conclusion:

The connection between Gandhi and other modern thinkers to the Indus Valley is a little bit tenuous but the argument can be made through the stronger connections of India’s spiritual development. From Vedic seers to Buddha and then classical India, Bhakti movement, Thoreau, and Gandhi, there is a tangible connection of Pacifism. This connection shows the intellectual continuity from ancient times to modern India. Ancient India's pacifism has influenced even modern India’s Non-aligned movement. We can see from the Indus Valley and later societies that

a living and vibrant philosophy or religion with openness is necessary for pacifism to operate in a society or culture.

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Glossary

- **Harrapans:** people of the Indus Valley civilization
- **Classic India:** 500 BC-500 AD. Era of Vedic Samkhya and then era of Buddhism (Indus valley thought influenced Vedic Samkhya and Buddhism, i.e. orthodox and hetero orthodox) metaphysics
- **Atma:** the ‘Self’ in pure consciousness
- **Jiva:** ‘life’/spirit
- **Upakar:** helping
- **Dharma:**
 - Simon: ‘methodology’ not set belief. Umbrella category to describe common indian methodology of caring about transcendental celestial duty as a primary. Transcendental soul’s obligations and duty
 - Rupam: to hold to one’s own principles and nature of duty
- **Sanatana Dharma:** umbrella term for all dharmic thought (Hinduism, Buddhism, Jainism, Sikhism)

Gods

- **Vishnu:** the ‘preserver’, primary of Vaishnavism. He is incarnated on earth as ‘avatars’
- **Shiva:** the ‘destroyer’, primary of Shaivism
- **Brahma:** the ‘creator’
- **Krishna:** an avatar of Vishnu, a Supreme God.

Texts

- **Sutras:** format of writing done in collections of short constructive aphorisms
- **Sastras:** standard format basically book essay or other prose
- **Sruti:** from the beginning; scripture
- **Smrti:** non scripture writings includes sastras kavya and sutras
- **Vedas:** hindu main scripture

- **Upanishads:** to sit down near latter part of vedas more philisophical
 - **Mundaka upanishad:** upanishad regarding self
- **Itihasas:** ‘as it happened’ historical accounts akin to odyssey and illiad
 - **Ramayana:** story of ramayana
 - **Mahabharata:** story of krishna and dwarka
- **Tantra:** method of worship relying on rituals/mantras (specific chants)

Figure 1: The weekly venue of our focused group discussion, the Red Rail Farm historic area, Lincoln, Massachusetts.

Figure 2: One of the weekly FGD sessions, 2023 (From left: Bikul, Simon, Marcie, Kim, Reya and Kevin).

Figure 3: One of the weekly FGD sessions, 2022, where Ms Lekhika Pathak of KaviKrishna Lab, Assam, India joined the team (from left, Kim, Marice, Lekhika and Simon).

Figure 4: One of the weekly FGD sessions through Zoom to include members of Muga Silk Museum, KaviKrishna Center of Indian Knowledge System, Sualkuchi, India.